

Chemical Investigation of the leaves of *Eugenia formosa* Wall.

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We have undertaken a thorough investigation^{1,2,3} of the controversial genus *Eugenia* (Fam. Myrtaceae) with a view to classify this genus by chemotaxonomic means. We now report the isolation of erythrodiol and betulinic acid from the leaves of *E. formosa*.

The isolation of erythrodiol in the free state is a rare phenomenon. It is known to occur as stearate in *Erythroxylon novogranatense*⁴ and *Haplophyton cimicidum*⁵, as glycoside in *Lemaireocereus longispinus*⁶, *L. hystrix*⁷, *Heliabravoa chende*⁸ (formerly *Lemaireocereus chende*), as 3-O-acetyl derivative in *Machaerium incorruptible*⁹ and as a monocaprylate in *Madhuca latifolia*¹⁰. Moreover, this diol has not been isolated from any plant belonging to Myrtaceae family either in the free or in the combined state. Thus we consider that the presence of erythrodiol in *E. formosa* may be of great significance from taxonomic stand point.

The neutral fraction of the plant extract on chromatography over alumina furnished only one solid material, m.p. 235°, C₃₀H₅₀O₂ (M⁺ 442). It showed pink coloration with Liebermann-Burchard reagent. IR spectrum is indicative of the presence of hydroxyl function (3500 cm⁻¹). The mass fragmentation pattern is in accordance with Δ¹²-unsaturated oleanene skeleton¹¹. The mass spectrum showed prominent ions at m/e 442, 87.5% (M⁺); 427, 10.2% (M⁺—CH₃); 424, 13.6% (M⁺—H₂O); 411, 82.9% (M⁺—CH₂OH); 393, 9.4% (M⁺—CH₂OH—H₂O); 234, 35.78% (retro-Diels Alder fragment, (a) 221, 13%, (b) 207, 60.2% (rupture of ring C, (c) 203, 100% (a—CH₂OH)); 189, 69.6% (a—CH₂OH—C—2H i.e., d, and c—H₂O) and three other ions at m/e 399, 12.5%; 385, 15.3%; and 220, 18.2% the genesis of those are not clear.

All these data in conjunction with the formation of diacetate, m.p. 183°, are definite proof of the identity of this compound with erythrodiol.

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The acidic fraction was esterified with diazomethane and chromatographed over deactivated alumina. The only solid, m.p. 219°, came out of the column was identified as methyl betulinate by elemental analysis, superimposable IR spectra, mixed m.p. determination and co-chromatography on a silica gel G plate.

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